

Document Definitions

Heading Definitions

General Definitions	External definitions for objects
Funder Standards	Funder-specific definitions of objects
Identification	Definitions and Quantity ID
Requirements	Funder-specific requirements for the objects depending on type.
Example of Actions for Authors with Instructions	Author-facing report outputs from DataSeer UI, grouped by object Action Requirement. These are included to connect the requirement rules with the specific actions requested of authors.

Other Definitions

Objects	Objects include trackable items required for compliance with Funder policy. Objects currently include Datasets , Code , Software , Lab Materials , and Protocols . Author information pertaining to Funder policies is also tracked.
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[ASAP Powerpoint for Sharing Requirements](#)

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Datasets

General Definitions

Wikipedia	A dataset (or data set) is a collection of data. In the case of tabular data, a dataset corresponds to one or more database tables, where every column of a table represents a particular variable, and each row corresponds to a given record of the dataset in question. The dataset lists values for each of the variables, such as for example height and weight of an object, for each member of the dataset. Datasets can also consist of a collection of documents or files.			
NIH Data Collection	Systematic gathering of data for a particular purpose from various sources, including questionnaires, interviews, observation, existing records, and electronic devices. The process is usually preliminary to statistical analysis of the data.			
DataSeer Definition	Our philosophy: data collection is an action where features of the real world (heights, reflectances, etc) are captured by some device and become data points in a computer. A collection of data points about the same object or class of objects is a dataset.			
Identifier Acronym Legend	DOI: Digital Object Identifier	URL: Uniform Resource	PID: Persistent (Permanent) Identifier	PMID: PubMed Reference Number ; PMCID: PubMed Central Reference Number

Funder Standards

Identification

New Datasets	Datasets generated within the study. These can range in type and can be further separated into Author Action Required categories based on datatypes or further curation.
Re-Use Datasets	Datasets used within the study that were generated in other publications or sources, requirements differ depending on datatype re-used.
Representative Images/Media	Visual and other datasets that sometimes require an incredible amount of space to store are not currently required to be included in repository uploads. Representative datasets can be New or Re-Use datasets. Examples of these datatypes include Image, Video, Sound.
Quality Control (QC) Datasets	Raw data from testing a sample of the output is not required, but measurements are recommended to be included to increase faith in results presented. All datatypes can appear in this category.
Confirmatory Datasets	Intermediate steps that produce data can be treated exactly the same as QC datasets. Examples of Confirmatory datasets include many assays, chromatography, genotyping, confirmatory sequencing , etc.
Dataset Object Quantities	Each object is counted, regardless of whether they are bundled (i.e. one DOI or URL) into a collection (then all objects within collection are counted).
PID Examples	Persistent identifiers include accession numbers and other dataset IDs. For re-use of certain datasets, website homepages are sufficient accession numbers as long as date accessed is also shared. ASAP-specific examples include AMP-PD (PPMI, PDBP, etc.), GP2 , Tracking Parkinsons and others.

Requirements

New Datasets	Depending on type, require raw data from experiments included in upload to Zenodo or other reputable repository with a PID, URL, or DOI included in the manuscript text.
Re-Use Datasets	Depending on type, require URL or link to dataset used, or DOI to article text and relevant query information including date downloaded.
Datasets with Optional Sharing Requirements	These datasets may be identified, but are not required to be included in repository upload by current Funder Standards. This includes media such as images and videos and datasets such as those created through confirmatory assays, chromatography, and various genetic methods.

Example Dataset Actions for Authors with Instructions

Action	Recommendation									
Yes	Deposit to appropriate repository and cite PID in text									
Instructions										
The ASAP-ZENODO Workspace is a great tool to learn how to deposit your data to Zenodo, please upload your data and include the permanent identifier (PID) in the manuscript text.										
#	Re-Use	QC	Rep	Issue	Dataset Name	Sentence from article text	URL	Unique Ident	Datatype	Notes
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Image Quantification	We quantified the images using ImageJ.			Tabular Data	

Action	Recommendation									
Yes	Cite dataset unique identifier in text									
Instructions										
Do these datasets also have additional citations ? Please be sure to include in each citation. If not, make sure you have included information on how each dataset was queried and the date downloaded.										
#	Re-Use	QC	Rep	Issue	Dataset Name	Sentence from article text	URL	Unique Ident	Datatype	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Reference Human Genome	We aligned the genes to the human genome of			Genetic Data	

Action	Recommendation									
Yes	Verify dataset citation									
Instructions										
It looks like there may be an issue with this citation. Please verify everything is up to date for publication and be sure to include a stable URL/Unique identifier in the manuscript text.										
#	Re-Use	QC	Rep	Issue	Dataset Name	Sentence from article text	URL	Unique Ident	Datatype	Notes
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Image Quantification	We quantified the images using ImageJ and ca	https://github.com/RLStein/		Tabular Data	The URL given leads to a 404 error.

Action	Recommendation									
No	Done - Cited correctly									
#	Re-Use	QC	Rep	Issue	Dataset Name	Sentence from article text	URL	Unique Ident	Datatype	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Reference Human Genome (G	We aligned the genes to the human genome G	https://ftp.ensembl.org/pub/		Genetic Data	

Action	Recommendation									
<i>Optional - Media</i>	Not required, but recommended to include the representative image/video files in raw format with dataset upload.									
Instructions										
It is recommended to include any image or video datasets from this table in your Zenodo upload and cite the permanent identifier (PID) in the manuscript text. The ASAP-ZENODO Workspace is a great tool to learn how.										
#	Re-Use	QC	Rep	Issue	Dataset Name	Sentence from article text	URL	Unique Ident	Datatype	Notes
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	HeLa DAPI Images	Cells were visualized with an Olympus XYJ Mic			Image: Microscopy	

Action	Recommendation									
<i>Optional - Other</i>	Confirmatory and Quality Control datasets are not required to be included in your dataset upload.									
Instructions										
Sharing confirmatory and QC datasets helps other researchers be confident in the quality of your work. The ASAP-ZENODO Workspace is a great tool to learn how to deposit your data.										
#	Re-Use	QC	Rep	Issue	Dataset Name	Sentence from article text	URL	Unique Ident	Datatype	Notes
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Bradford Assay	Cells were assessed through Bradford Assay u			Tabular Data: Assa	

Code and Software

General Definitions

Code	Custom defined rules, defined parameters, scripts, etc., that run on software or software packages as command.			
Software	Programs and other operating information used by computers - including programs, databases, and tools.			
Software Package	Collections of files and information about the software and those files - including command-line packages and models.			
Identifier Acronym Legend	DOI: Digital Object Identifier	URL: Uniform Resource Locator	RRID: Research Resource Identifiers	PID: Persistent (Permanent) Identifier

Funder Standards

Identification	
New Code	Using command-line software indicates that the authors must have custom scripts (which they wrote to operate the software), and these scripts need to be shared.
Re-Use Code	Very rare, because re-using scripts requires creating new scripts as a wrapper (as above). But if this object is identified, it is labeled as the re-use of scripts or a software package.
New Software	New code outputs created using ASAP funds. Including software, packages, sites, databases, and other resources.
Re-Use Software	The use of any software in the analysis of data or in running simulations must be adequately cited.
Code Object Quantities	New scripts are assumed to be generated for every new command-line software mentioned, but all scripts/code can be included in single Zenodo upload as one file (i.e. multiple scripts can have the same DOI).
Code Re-Use Object Quantities	When authors describe using someone else's code, they must include the reworked scripts in their Zenodo upload. I.e. code re-use indicates the generation of new scripts to be included in any repository uploads. When someone else's scripts are used, this creates 2 objects - the re-use citation and the rework of the script (a new script).
Software Object Quantities	Each new software mention is its own object.
Software Re-Use Object Quantities	If a software package is mentioned, host software is required as an object.

Sharing Requirements

New Code	Although GitHub is an industry-accepted repository, it's not entirely suitable for policy standards as uploads are easily changed after publication. All new code and scripts must be included in the Zenodo upload or an archived GitHub, the DOI must then be provided in the manuscript - a GitHub link be included in addition to the Zenodo DOI, but solely the Zenodo DOI is acceptable.
Re-Use Code	Adequately citing the re-use of code involves including the URL (and version if applicable).
New Software	The tool's version, URL, and a generated RRID are required to be included in the manuscript. New software is required to be registered for an RRID with exceptions (an appropriate DOI can sometimes replace RRID).
Re-Use Software	Software requires an RRID (if applicable), Version, and an URL. Alternatively, a DOI to the article sharing the software is acceptable in some cases instead of an RRID. The version is still required regardless of permanent identifiers.

Example Code and Software Actions for Authors with Instructions

New Code

Action	Recommendation					
Yes	Upload code to Zenodo and provide DOI					
Instructions						
Include any source and relevant code in the upload to Zenodo. If you're unsure where to start, go to the ASAP-ZENODO Workspace for more detailed instructions. Include the Zenodo DOI in the manuscript text.						
#	Issue	Object Name	Sentence from article text	DOI	URL	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Custom Scripts	All analyses were performed in R (v 4.0.5)			

Action	Recommendation					
Yes	Verify citation					
Instructions						
There seems to be an issue with the information provided, please make sure any identifiers are functional and include a stable DOI in the manuscript text						
#	Issue	Object Name	Sentence from article text	DOI	URL	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Custom Scripts	We quantified the images using R and scr		https://github.com/RLStein/goosebumps	The URL given leads to a 404 error

Action	Recommendation					
No	Done - Cited correctly					
#	Issue	Object Name	Sentence from article text	DOI	URL	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Custom Scripts	All analyses were performed in R (v 4.0.5)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.632295		

Software and Re-Use Code

Action	Recommendation									
Yes	Register tool to get missing information									
Instructions										
Click here to register your tool(s) to get an RRID and a stable URL. Include the RRID, a stable URL, and a Version # (where applicable) in the manuscript text.										
#	Re-Use	Version	Issue	Software Name	Sentence from article text	URL	RRID (if applicable)	Name of Entity Identifier	Suggested RRID Citation	Suggested URL
1	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	vandross package	We created the vandross package to give					

Action	Recommendation									
Yes	Include missing information in citation									
Instructions										
Include the Version#, a stable URL, and an RRID (where possible) in your manuscript text for each citation. Please click here to see if the software has an RRID and include it in your manuscript text if it exists.										
#	Re-Use	Version	Issue	Software Name	Sentence from article text	URL	RRID (if applicable)	Name of Entity Identifier	Suggested RRID Citation	Suggested URL
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	v 4.0.5	<input type="checkbox"/>	R (v 4.0.5)	All analyses were performed in R (v 4.0.5)			R Project for Statistical Computing	R Project for Statistical Computing (RRID:SCR_001905)	

Action	Recommendation									
Yes	Verify citation									
Instructions										
There seems to be an issue with the information provided, please make sure any identifiers are functional and include a stable URL for new software in the manuscript text.										
#	Re-Use	Version	Issue	Software Name	Sentence from article text	URL	RRID (if applicable)	Name of Entity Identifier	Suggested RRID Citation	Suggested URL
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	v 4.0.5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	R (v 4.0.5)	All analyses were performed in R (v 4.0.5)	http://www.r-project.org/	RRID:SCR_001901	R Project for Statistical Computing	R Project for Statistical Computing (RRID:SCR_001905)	

Action	Recommendation									
No	Done - Cited correctly									
#	Re-Use	Version	Issue	Software Name	Sentence from article text	URL	RRID (if applicable)	Name of Entity Identifier	Suggested RRID Citation	Suggested URL
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	v 4.0.5	<input type="checkbox"/>	R (v 4.0.5)	All analyses were performed in R (v 4.0.5)	http://www.r-project.org/	(RRID:SCR_001905)			

Action	Recommendation									
No	None - Citation meets minimum standards									
Instructions										
There is still information missing from these citations, but they are counted as shared because the necessary information may be unavailable or not applicable.										
#	Re-Use	Version	Issue	Software Name	Sentence from article text	URL	RRID (if applicable)	Name of Entity Identifier	Suggested RRID Citation	Suggested URL
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	R	All analyses were performed in R		(RRID:SCR_001905)			

Lab Materials

General Definitions

Model Organism	A model organism (often shortened to model) is a non-human species that is extensively studied to understand particular biological phenomena, with the expectation that discoveries made in the model organism will provide insight into the workings of other organisms.			
Cell Line	Cell line is a general term that applies to a defined population of cells that can be maintained in culture for an extended period of time, retaining stability of certain phenotypes and functions. Cell lines are usually clonal, meaning that the entire population originated from a single common ancestor cell.			
Plasmid	A plasmid is a small, extrachromosomal DNA molecule within a cell that is physically separated from chromosomal DNA and can replicate independently.			
Antibody	An antibody is a protein produced by the body's immune system when it detects harmful substances, called antigens. Examples of antigens include microorganisms (bacteria, fungi, parasites, and viruses) and chemicals.			
Constructs and Cultures	To be found (tbf)			
Tools & Reagents	Equipment, Reagents, Tools, Kits, Oligonucleotides, and other items used during experiments.			
Identifier Legend	DOI: Digital Object Identifier	URL: Uniform Resource Locator	RRID: Research Resource Identifiers	Cat#: Catalog Number

Funder Standards

Identification

New Resource	Stable resources generated using ASAP funds.
Re-Use - Another Lab	Common language includes: "was a gift from" etc., often these resources aren't registered with RRIDs.
Re-Use - Commercial Source	If a Commercial Source was used, it's assumed the resource has a Catalog number that can be used to search for an RRID.
Resource Types	
Organism	If Catalog number present, search SciCrunch for RRID, if no RRID, resource meets minimum standards with Source and Catalog number in text.
Cell Line	Stable cell lines also include those through bacterial strains.
Plasmid	Vectors and recombinant objects are sometimes referred to as plasmids for tracking purposes.
Antibody	Both primary and secondary antibodies are tracked, understood that this category is hardest to track.
Constructs and Cultures	Transient (nonstable) generations such as neuronal cultures, fibroblast cultures, etc. - not formally tracked, but included on Summary Tab of Report
Tools & Reagents	Not currently tracked. These include kits, equipment, tools, medium, oligos, etc.
Lab Material Object Quantities	Language involving crosses means 3 separate objects are identified: the 2 re-used objects and the newly generated object. New mentions of re-used resources count once per manuscript. It is recommended that authors include a Key Resource Table in their manuscripts - especially when using large quantities of different trackable lab resources.

Requirements

New Resource	Register resource with SciCrunch and include the RRID in the text, Source and Catalog number are not required. Requirements do not differ depending on resource type generated.
Re-Use Resource	If Catalog number present, search Scicrunch for RRID, if no RRID, resource meets minimum standards with Source and Catalog number in text.

Example Lab Material Actions for Authors with Instructions

Action	Recommendation										
Yes	Assign RRID and cite in text										
Instructions											
Register your resource(s) using SciCrunch , be sure to include the RRID and Cat# in your manuscript.											
#	Re-Use	Issue	Material Name	Sentence from article text	Source	Catalog Number	RRID	Datatype	Name of Entity Identified	Suggested RRID Citation	Notes
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	HEK293 cell line	We generated a stable HEK293	This study			Lab Materials: Cel	HEK293		

Action	Recommendation										
Yes	Check for an existing RRID										
Instructions											
Check SciCrunch to make sure your citations include the RRID (if available). If the resource was commercially purchased, include the Cat# in your manuscript. If your resource was a gift from another lab, it may still have an associated RRID in the SciCrunch database.											
#	Re-Use	Issue	Material Name	Sentence from article text	Source	Catalog Number	RRID	Datatype	Name of Entity Identified	Suggested RRID Citation	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	P(TRIP.JF01701) files	The following strain was obtained	Bloomington Dros			Lab Materials: Org	P{TRIP.JF01701}	RRID:BDSC_3140	

Action	Recommendation										
Yes	Verify citation										
Instructions											
There seems to be an issue with the information provided, please make sure each citation includes the correct RRID and/or Catalog Number are included in the manuscript text.											
#	Re-Use	Issue	Material Name	Sentence from article text	Source	Catalog Number	RRID	Datatype	Name of Entity Identified	Suggested RRID Citation	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	rabbit anti KAT8	The following antibodies were used	Abcam	ab200600		Lab Materials: Anti	Recombinant Anti-	(Abcam Cat# ab20	The catalog number in the r

Action	Recommendation										
No	Done - Cited correctly										
#	Re-Use	Issue	Material Name	Sentence from article text	Source	Catalog Number	RRID	Datatype	Name of Entity Identified	Suggested RRID Citation	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	rabbit anti KAT8	The following antibodies were used	Abcam	ab200660	RRID:AB_2891127	Lab Materials: Anti			

Action	Recommendation										
No	None - Citation meets minimum standards										
Instructions											
There is still information missing from these citations, but they are counted as shared because the necessary information may be unavailable or not applicable.											
#	Re-Use	Issue	Material Name	Sentence from article text	Source	Catalog Number	RRID	Datatype	Name of Entity Identified	Suggested RRID Citation	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	P(TRIP.JF01701) files	The following strain was obtained	Bloomington Dros		RRID:BDSC_3140	Lab Materials: Org			

Protocols

General Definition

Protocol (science)	In natural and social science research, a protocol is most commonly a predefined procedural method in the design and implementation of an experiment.	
Identifier Acronym Legend	DOI: Digital Object Identifier	URL: Uniform Resource Locator

Funder Standards

Identification

New Protocol	A new protocol is likely to have been followed when that section of the Methods doesn't mention another protocol or manufacturer's instructions.
Re-Use - Published Protocol	When the section mentions a published article or some other permanent identifier to a published protocol.
Re-Use - Manufacturer's Instructions	The section may mention performing that part of the experiment according to the manufacturer's instructions, in this case the re-used protocol is currently cited correctly.
Re-Use - Survey/Questionnaire Question	The questions asked in order to obtain Survey and Questionnaire data should be adequately cited or shared, and are therefore considered protocols.
Protocol Object Quantities	A protocol is required for every Methods Section Heading in lab experiment (wet lab) manuscripts. Exceptions include lists of reagents, data manipulation, and statistical analyses sections

Requirements

New Protocols	DOI or URL to protocols.io unless manufacturer's instructions or the referenced published article is an authorized Methods article.
Re-Use - Published Protocol	Citation to a Methods article is sufficient, DOI or URL recommended.
Re-Use - Manufacturer's Instructions	Reference to Manufacturer is currently a sufficient citation.
Re-Use - Survey/Questionnaire Question	TBD.

Example Protocol Actions for Authors with Instructions

Action				Recommendation	
Yes	Deposit in repository and cite DOI in text				
Instructions					
Check if a protocol exists on protocols.io to cite, if not, please upload your protocol directly to protocols.io and click "Get DOI". Then include the DOI (linking URL) in the manuscript text. Note that you can also generate a collection on protocols.io and cite the collection directly instead for all methods associated with the manuscript.					
#	Re-Use	Issue	Methods Section Heading	Repository URL, DOI, or Citation	Notes
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Immunofluorescence		

Action				Recommendation	
Yes	Include missing information in citation				
Instructions					
Make sure the paper cited is the Methods paper related to each protocol, otherwise check protocols.io for an existing protocol. Then include the DOI (linking URL) in the manuscript text.					
#	Re-Use	Issue	Methods Section Heading	Repository URL, DOI, or Citation	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Mass Spectrometry	(Smith et al. 2010)	

Action				Recommendation	
Yes	Verify citation				
Instructions					
There seems to be an issue with the information provided, please ensure a stable DOI/URL or reference is included in manuscript text.					
#	Re-Use	Issue	Methods Section Heading	Repository URL, DOI, or Citation	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ELISA	https://www.protocols.io/view/elisa-protocol-8qpvrwkolmkn/v1	The URL given leads to a 404 error.

Action				Recommendation	
No	Done - Cited correctly				
#	Re-Use	Issue	Methods Section Heading	Repository URL, DOI, or Citation	Notes
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	ELISA	https://www.protocols.io/view/elisa-protocol-6qpvrwkolmkn/v1	
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Immunofluorescence	manufacturer's instructions	

ASAP Funding Acknowledgement, Affiliation, & Article License, ORCIDs

Definitions	
Acknowledgement	Funder-specific language in the manuscript denoting whether the Grant is acknowledged for the objects generated using Grant funds.
Affiliation	Funder-specific language in the Author List of the manuscript describing an author's association with the Funder.
License	Copyright licenses involve the terms and services involved in the manuscript's publication. Creative Commons CC are used in Academic Publishing.
ORCID	ORCIDs are PIDs for authors.

Funder Standards

Requirements - Special cases	
Acknowledgement	GP2 and PPMI cohorts require different language than the ASAP cohort.
Affiliation	GP2 and PPMI cohorts require different language than the ASAP cohort.
License	ASAP articles require a CC-BY license for preprints and publications, a CC-ND license is accepted in certain cases.

Requirements - Specific language	
Acknowledgement	This research was funded in whole or in part by Aligning Science Across Parkinson's [Grant number] through the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research (MJFF). For the purpose of open access, the author has applied a CC BY [replace with CC0 if appropriate] public copyright license to all Author Accepted Manuscripts arising from this submission.
Affiliation	Aligning Science Across Parkinson's (ASAP) Collaborative Research Network, Chevy Chase, MD, 20815
License	CC-BY 4.0
ORCID Requirements	If authors are included in ASAP Network, they are required to have their ORCID in the manuscript for tracking purposes.

Example Output

	Action Required?	Recommendati	Language Used	Language Required	Notes
Acknowledgement	No			This research was funded in whole or in part by Aligning Science Across Parkinson's [Grant number] through the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research (MJFF). For the purpose of open access, the author has applied a CC BY public copyright license to all Author Accepted Manuscripts arising from this submission.	
Affiliation	No			Aligning Science Across Parkinson's (ASAP) Collaborative Research Network, Chevy Chase, MD, 20815	
License	No			CC-BY 4.0	

Author	ASAP Affiliation Listed in ms	Part of ASAP Network	ORCID in ms?	Suggested ORCID
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		